

Seed characterisation and micromorphology of taxa of the genus *Crocus* (Iridaceae) in Bulgarian flora

Tsvetanka Raycheva¹, Kiril Stoyanov²

(1) Department of Botany and Agrometeorology, Agricultural University – Plovdiv, Bulgaria, raicheva.tzveta@gmail.com

(2) [Corresponding author] Department of Botany and Agrometeorology, Agricultural University – Plovdiv, Bulgaria, nomtax@gmail.com

Abstract: The morphology of seeds and SEM structure of epicuticular formations of the seed testa of 14 species of *Crocus* genus known so far for Bulgaria have been studied. The results have demonstrated great diversity. This study provided additional characteristics for the taxonomy of the crocuses that would be particularly useful for distinguishing some morphologically similar and critical species. A great diversity has been observed in the sculpturing pattern of the seed surface in the taxa studied. Discreet characters relevant to *Crocus* taxonomy have been revealed. The established differences in the microsurface structures correspond to differences in the metric and qualitative characteristics of the seeds in the studied taxa. Some of the investigated species of the genus *Crocus* in Bulgaria have been investigated for the first time by seed morphology. It follows from the obtained results that the morphological characteristics of the seeds are closely related to the taxonomy of the genus. As a result of the research, we proposed an analytical key for the recognition of the characteristics of the seeds.

Keywords: analytical key, Bulgarian flora, *Crocus*, seed coat, seed morphology, SEM

Introduction

Crocus L. (Iridaceae) comprises 235 taxa (Rukšāns, 2017) and is distributed from West Europe and North-west Africa to West China. The traditional morphological approach creates difficulties in distinguishing *Crocus* species and is the cause of discussions in their classification (Harpke et al., 2012). In this regard, additional characteristics are necessary that would assist in species differentiation and classification.

Seed morphology has been highlighted as a diagnostic feature in the taxonomy of crocuses (Maw, 1886). However, except for a few studies (Bojňanský & Fargašova, 2007; Kujat & Rafiński, 1978; Grilli Caiola et al., 2010; Carta et al., 2015; Karaismailoğlu et al., 2018), *Crocus* seeds have not been popular as a research subject. Seed collection in natural populations is made difficult by the fact that the capsules and seeds of autumn or spring flowering crocuses reach maturity in April and May – 3–5 months after the bloom (Kerndorff et al., 2015; Mathew, 1982). Seed colour and size may vary within a taxon, but patterns

of diversity in caruncle development are diagnostic of *Crocus* species (Maw, 1886). In our experience from field observations, it is difficult to spot and collect pods when the vegetation is thick and tall and the seeds are shed after the fruit bursts open. Therefore, research on crocus seeds requires the cultivation of taxa from natural populations, and the collection of capsules and seeds must be done carefully. In the period 2019–2023, we have collected materials from the 14 known taxa, including 3 new ones for the flora of Bulgaria (*C. adamioides*, *C. speciosus* and *C. heuffelianus*). Seed testa structures and epidermal cell types may allow the establishment of phylogenetic relationships among flowering plant taxa and may provide valuable information on *Crocus* taxonomy (Carta et al., 2015; Karaismailoğlu & Gemicioğlu, 2018). In addition, this parameter is hardly affected by modification variability under the influence of external environmental factors (Kerndorff et al., 2015).

Bearing in mind the importance of the morphology of the seeds, which is a conservative criterion in the taxonomy of crocuses, as well as the unresolved

phylogenetic relationships, we undertook a study of the seeds of the Bulgarian species, for the bigger part of which there are no previous studies. We aim to describe the morphology of the seeds, find characters of systematic importance and evaluate their usefulness in confirming or limiting the taxonomic classification of the taxa of the *Crocus* genus known for the Bulgarian flora.

Material and methods

Sample collection

The seeds of 14 *Crocus* species have been included in the comparative study. The seeds were carefully collected between 2019 and 2023 from the natural populations during targeted taxonomic studies of the genus *Crocus* in Bulgaria. Collected plants have been cultivated in a garden. The seeds have been collected immediately before the pods burst. Some of the seeds have been collected directly from the habitat. Voucher specimens have been deposited in the herbarium SOA and described below as follows: region, MGRS square, nearest geographic name, altitude, decimal coordinates (N E), date (collectors monograms), herbarium code and catalogue number of specimens. The vouchers of the SEM study are marked with an asterisk (*):

Crocus adamioides Kernd. & Pasche

Toundja Hilly Country: 35TMG43, Moustrak Village, 306 m, 41.87795 26.29031, 2020-02-04 (R,S) SOA 062716*.

Crocus chrysanthus Herb.

Stara Planina (central): 35TLH53, Ispolin Peak, 1523 m, 42.7386111 25.25222, 2018-04-05 (R,S) SOA 062487; Rhodopi Mts (central): 35TKG95, Perestitsa Fortress, 808 m, 42.030938 24.534379, 2020-02-22 (R,S) SOA 062739*.

Crocus danubensis Kernd., Pasche, Randjel. & V.Randjel.

Northeast Bulgaria: 35TMJ14, Basarbovo Village, 110 m, 43.75492 25.94889, 2021-02-09 (R,S) SOA 063090*.

Crocus flavus Weston

Rhodopi Mts (central): 35TKG95, Perestitsa Fortress, 812 m, 42.02534 24.54629, 2019-03-24 (R,S) SOA 062605*, Peroushtitsa, 386 m, 42.04874 24.54127, 2020-02-22 (R,S) SOA 062831.

Toundja Hilly Country: 35TMG56, Golemiya Kamak locality - Knyazhevo, 98 m, 42.09852 26.50603, 2020-02-03 (R,S) SOA 062717*.

Crocus heuffelianus Herb.

Pirin Mt (northern): 34TGM12, Mogilata Peak – Dobrinishte, 1015 m, 41.78486 23.55544, 2023-03-17 (S,R) SOA 063348*.

Crocus olivieri J.Gay

Black Sea Coast (south): 35TNG85, Sekana Koriya locality, Sinemorets, 32 m, 42.06109 27.96935, 2020-02-14 (R,S) SOA 062809*.

Thracian lowland: 35TKG96, Shirokiya Peak – Novo Selo, 358 m, 42.09505 24.46522, 2019-02-17 (R,S) SOA 062593; 42.09797 24.46721, 2020-02-22 (R,S) SOA 062738*.

Crocus pallasii Goldb.

Balkan Range (eastern): 35TMH42, Hamam Bair Peak – Sliven City, 290 m, 42.6730389 26.3105556, 2020-10-21 (I. Kostadinov) SOA 062994.

Rhodopi Mts (central): 35TLG15, Gulubovo Village, 597 m, 42.0305278 24.7234167, 2018-11-10 (R) SOA 062431*; 35TLG25, Asenovgrad Town, 359 m, 41.99407 24.86893, 2019-11-10 (S) SOA 062675.

Thracian Lowland: 35TLG16, Bounardjik Hill, 205 m, 42.14553 24.73884, 2018-10-31 (R,S) SOA 062436.

Crocus pallidus Kitan. & Drenkovski

Black Sea Coast (northern): 35TPJ21, Kamen Bryag Village, 41 m, 43.45199 28.54402, 2020-02-28 (R,S) SOA 062791*.

Crocus pulchellus Herb.

Thracian Lowland: 35TLG85, Brod Village, 127 m, 42.05697 25.66899, 2019-10-09 (R,S) SOA 063313.

Rhodopi Mts (western): 35TKG57, Semchinovo Village, 539 m, 42.16295 24.08936, 2020-11-02 (R,S) sn 2020.500.

Sredna Gora (western): 35TKG89, Strelcha Town, 420 m, 42.4027778 24.3836111, 2022-05-12 (R,S) sn 2022.113.

The valley of Strouma River (southern): 34TFL78, Loudo Dere, 390 m, 41.36614 23.1246, 2022-03-28 (R,S), sn 2022.038.

Rhodopi Mts (eastern): 35TMG12, Glouhite Kamani locality, 554 m, 41.7317 25.9689, 554 m, 2019-11-14 (R,S) SOA 062842*.

Crocus randjeloviciorum Kernd., Pasche, Harpke & Raca

Balkan Range (west): 34TFN76, Shilni Peak, 1005 m, 43.01154 23.12118, 2020-03-12 (R,S) SOA 062856*.
Crocus speciosus M.Bieb.

Black Sea Coast (southern): 35TNG85, Sekana Koriya locality, 37 m, 42.06027 27.97088, 2022-10-21 (R,S) SOA 063308*; 42.06009 27.96753, 2022-10-21 (R,S) SOA 063309.

Crocus tommasinianus Herb.

Balkan Foothill Region (western): 34TFP15, Vagleshtarnika locality, 377 m, 43.80896 22.39386, 2020-02-29 (R,S) SOA 062848*.

Crocus variegatus Hoppe & Hornsch.

Balkan Range (western): 34TFN97, Lakatnik Village, 738 m, 43.093102 23.387175, 2021-02-24 (R,S) SOA 063077*.

Crocus veluchensis Herb.

Rhodopi Mts (western): 35TKG84, Atoluka locality 1354 m, 41.9578778 24.3486111, 2020-06-19 (R,S) SOA 063208*.

Rhodopi Mts (central): 35TLG11, Rozhen locality, 1425 m, 41.67148 24.72673, 2021-06-11 (R,S) SOA 063158.

Morphological observations

Seeds have been examined, photographed and measured with a Leica EZ4W digital stereo microscope.

Selected seeds were photographed in 5 focus steps using Leica Application Suite (version 3.4.0), Leica Microsystems (2016), and the images have been stacked for a better contrast. The parameters on 20 representative seeds from a population sample of each species have been measured – main axis length, seed shape, testa colour, presence or absence of caruncle, raphe shape and dimensions. Micam 2.4 software (van Westen, 2009), calibrated for the respective magnifications, was used for the metric measurements. Seeds have been measured in general outline – longest and widest axis (together with the caruncle, funiculus and raphe). Because the shape of the caruncle, funiculus, and raphe varies greatly, they have not been considered when reporting representative values for seed length and width. The shape of the seeds has been valued in percentages using length to width ratio.

Scanning electron microscopy

Sample seeds have been prepared for scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis. The materials have been covered with a gold coating with a thickness of about 10nm in a vacuum evaporator in an argon ionising medium.

The samples have been fixed on coverslips with silver glue, and prepared for observation immediately before scanning. Observation and documentation have been performed with a Hitachi TM4000 electron microscope, in the Faculty of Chemistry, Sofia University. The information for each observation is shown on the photo marker – accelerating voltage 15 kV, type of BSE detector and magnification.

The character of the indumentum and the submicroscopic sculpture of the epidermal cells, expressed in the position of their periclinal walls, the position and features of the anticlinal walls and the presence or absence of epicuticular wax formations, the description of which is according to Barthlott's classification, are reported (Barthlott, 1981, 1998). Papillae were counted in $30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ sections and recalculated for an area of $1000 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Results

In general, seed size and shape (Figs 1–2) and surface sculpturing (Figs 3–9) in the species studied were more or less distinct and consistent across the studied

taxa. The results of the measurements are shown in Table 1. The observations are described below.

Ser. *Flavi* Mathew

C. flavus: Seeds $1.7\text{--}3.1 \times 1.2\text{--}2.5$ mm, with a ratio of 62–104%, red-brown. Caruncle, raphe and funiculus are distinct, the same colour as the rest of the seed, total $2.8\text{--}5.12 \times 1.5\text{--}3$ mm (Fig. 1A). The seed surface is covered with sparsely spaced cylindrical, long hairs, 0–1(–3) per 1000 μm^2 each (Fig. 3A).

C. olivieri: Seeds $1.6\text{--}2 \times 1\text{--}1.6$ mm, with a ratio of 61–81%, dark brown. Caruncle, raphe and funiculus slightly darker than rest of seed, total $2.4\text{--}2.9 \times 1.2\text{--}1.6$ mm (Fig. 1B). Seed surface glabrous, with densely oriented dome-shaped cells with secondary punctate structures, 1–8 per 1000 μm^2 each (Fig. 3B).

Ser. *Scardici* Mathew

C. pallasii: Seeds $1.9\text{--}3.1 \times 1.6\text{--}2.6$ mm, with a ratio of 75–98%, dark brown. Caruncle, raphe and funiculus, same colour as rest of seed, total $2.5\text{--}4.5 \times 1.9\text{--}2.9$ mm (Fig. 1C). Seed surface with numerous long hairs, thin flat and twisted cylindrically lengthwise, 7–16 per 1000 μm^2 . The coat cells from which the hairs emerge have a concave central part (Fig. 4A).

Ser. *Reticulati* Mathew

C. veluchensis: Seeds $1.8\text{--}3.1 \times 1.4\text{--}2.6$ mm, with ratio 57–107%, brown (Fig. 1D). Caruncle large, bright. Raphe and funiculus brown. Total size $2.4\text{--}3.6 \times 1.5\text{--}3.3$ mm. Surface glossy, reticulate, with relatively regular hexagonal plates, without papillae (Fig. 4B).

C. variegatus: Seeds $2.3\text{--}2.5 \times 2.1\text{--}2.6$ mm, with a ratio of 85–105%, brown. Caruncle, funiculus and raphe lighter than rest of seed, total size $3\text{--}3.3 \times 2.2\text{--}2.6$ mm (Fig. 1E); Surface dull, covered by 9–18 papillae per 1000 μm^2 (Fig. 5A).

C. danubensis: Seeds $2.4\text{--}2.5 \times 2.1\text{--}2.4$ mm, oval, with a ratio of 85–95%, brown. Caruncle, funiculus, and raphe lighter than rest of seed, total $3.4\text{--}3.6 \times 2.2\text{--}2.3$ mm (Fig. 1F). Surface matte, covered with 10–18 papillae per 1000 μm^2 (Fig. 5B).

Ser. *Verni* Mathew

C. heuffelianus: Seeds $1.6\text{--}2.3 \times 1.3\text{--}2$ mm, with a ratio of 70–95%, light brown to brown (Fig. 1G). Raphe visible, narrow. Caruncle and funiculus clearly developed, similarly coloured, total $1.8\text{--}2.5 \times 1.3\text{--}2.1$ mm. Surface of sparse flat hairs with expanded base and twist at tip, 3–10 per 1000 μm^2 (Fig. 6A).

C. tommasinianus: Seeds $1.6\text{--}2.3 \times 1.4\text{--}2.1$ mm, with a ratio of 53–100%, light brown to brown. Raphe distinct, narrow. Caruncle and funiculus distinct, similarly coloured, total $2.1\text{--}3.1 \times 1.4\text{--}2.1$ (Fig. 1). Surface of dense, scaly-tongued papillae with parallel folds and expanded base, 10–18 papillae per 1000 μm^2 (Fig. 6B).

Ser. *Speciosi* Mathew

C. pulchellus: Seeds $1.5\text{--}2.5 \times 1.2\text{--}1.9$ mm, with a ratio of 66–108%, almost spherical, brown. Raphe inconspicuous. Caruncle relatively small, same colour as rest of seed, total $1.9\text{--}3.3 \times 1.3\text{--}2$ mm (Fig. 2A). Surface with secondary dome-shaped structures with punctate cuticular growths, 8–19 per 1000 μm^2 each (Fig. 7A).

C. speciosus subsp. *ibrahimii*: Seeds $1.7\text{--}2.3 \times 1.4\text{--}2$ mm, with a ratio of 75–103%, almost spherical, brown. Caruncle relatively small, same colour as rest of seed, total $2.1\text{--}2.7 \times 1.5\text{--}2.1$ mm (Fig. 2B). Surface of dense conical papillae of 4–17 per 1000 μm^2 , with expanded base and rounded apex and irregular longitudinal folds (Fig. 7B).

Ser. *Biflori* Mathew

C. adamioides: Seeds ovate, $1.7\text{--}2 \times 1.2\text{--}1.6$ mm, with a ratio of 68–91%, reddish-brown (Fig. 2C). Caruncle, funiculus and raphe clearly visible, similarly coloured, total $2.3\text{--}2.9 \times 1.2\text{--}1.7$ mm. The surface with indistinct slightly irregularly delineated cells with dispersed formations of cuticular rod-like, scale-like and band-like outgrowths of 13–27 per 1000 μm^2 (Fig. 8A).

C. randjelovicorum: Seeds spherical to ovate, $1\text{--}1.8 \times 1\text{--}1.6$ mm, with a ratio of 68–107%. Caruncle, raphe and funiculus are clearly visible, and similarly coloured, a total of $8\text{--}2.3 \times 1.1\text{--}1.7$ mm (Fig. 2D). Microscopically, a hairy surface is observed, and

Fig. 1. Seeds of *C. flavus* (A), *C. olivieri* (B), *C. pallasii* (C), *C. veluchensis* (D), *C. danubensis* (E), *C. variegatus* (F), *C. heuffelianus* (G), *C. tommasinianus* (H).

Fig. 2. Seeds of *C. pulchellus* (A), *C. speciosus* subsp. *ibrahimii* (B), *C. adamioides* (C), *C. randjeloviciorum* (D), *C. chrysanthus* (E), *C. pallidus* (F).

submicroscopic structures pitted undulating folds of 7–12 per 1000 μm^2 , with secondary needle-like and band-like cuticular growths. (Fig. 8B).

C. chrysanthus: Seeds narrowly elliptic, 1.7–3.3 \times 1.1–1.6 mm, with a ratio of 45–66%, red to dark brown (Fig. 2E). Rapha, caruncle, and funiculus

inconspicuous, similarly coloured, total 2.3–3.9 \times 1.1–1.8 mm. Surface with long conical papillae 10–18 per 1000 μm^2 , with expanded base and secondary cuticular deposits at apex, with numerous secondary cuticular scale-like or band-like shorter processes between them (Fig. 9A).

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of the seeds of *C. flavus* (A) and *C. olivieri* (B).

C. pallidus: Seeds ovate, 1.7–2.1 × 1.2–1.9 mm, with a ratio of 72–97%, rounded, brown. Funiculus, caruncle and raphe visible, total 2.2–2.7 × 1.3–2 mm. Surface of numerous short conical papillae, 9–22 per 1000 µm².

In general, the types of SEM sculptures in our species are of 4 types – cone-shaped hairs with an expanded base, tongue-band-shaped with a spiral twist along the entire length, cylindrical hairs and smooth.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of the seeds of *C. pallasii* (A) and *C. veluchensis* (B).

Discussion

Light microscopic observations of the studied species show differences in the colour of the seed testa, different degrees of development of the caruncle and

raphe, as well as the differentiation of papillae and hairs on the surface. These differences are too small for species discrimination with reflected light observations. The colour of the seeds in the studied species is reddish to reddish-brown, with varying

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs of the seeds of *C. danubensis* (A) and *C. variegatus* (B).

intensity in the samples. Despite the constancy of this parameter in some of the examined species, for example – the always reddish seeds of *C. chrysanthus*, it could not be a reliable characteristic for distinguishing.

The shape of the seeds is rotundate to ovate, as seen from the metric values in Table 1. Seed sizes range from 1.6 to 3 mm long and 1.1 to 2.6 mm wide. The ratio between these two values determines the shape of the seeds from ro-

Fig. 6. SEM micrographs of the seeds of *C. heuffelianus* (A) and *C. tommasinianus* (B).

tundate to elongated-elliptical. *Crocus chrysanthus* has the most elongated seeds. On the other side, the seeds of ser. *Reticulati* are rotundate. The members of ser. *Scardici* and *Reticulati* have the biggest seeds.

A distinguishing characteristic of seeds in the genus *Crocus* is the presence of raphe and caruncle. The raphe is the result of a sheet-like growth of the integument in the funiculus zone, with the growth starting from the two poles – micropyle and chalaza,

Fig. 7. SEM micrographs of the seeds of *C. pulchellus* (A) and *C. speciosus* subsp. *ibrahimii* (B).

which in some species do not merge. In *C. flavus* and *C. veluchensis*, the raphe has fused borders from the chalasal pole to the micropyle pole and is larger than in the other species. The smallest raphe has been observed in ser. *Biflori*, as in *C. chrysanthus* is faintly

noticeable in the shape of a longitudinal edge. The caruncle is always clearly visible in the micropyle area.

The examined seeds have been differentiated into morphological types using SEM. This study is the

Fig. 8. SEM micrographs of the seeds of *C. adamioides* (A) and *C. randjeloviciorum* (B).

first for some *Crocus* species. Accordingly, there are no detailed basic comparative descriptions. The outer epidermis of the testis forms papillae or hairs of various shapes – straight, twisted, raised, wavy, tongue-shaped, polygonal crushed.

Series *Reticulati* Matthew includes the critical taxa *C. variegatus* and *C. danubensis* until recently considered *C. reticulatus* (Stoyanov et al., 2020). Seed morphology provides definitive differences between the two taxa. The seeds of *C. danubensis*

Fig. 9. SEM micrographs of the seeds of *C. chrysanthus* (A) and *C. pallidus* (B).

have a well-developed caruncle and raphe, and the micromorphology of the seed surface has densely spaced short hairs with an expanded base and a pronounced waxy tip. In *C. variegatus* the hairs are sparser, with a broad base and lingually rounded,

without waxes at the apex, the caruncle and raphe less developed than in *C. danubensis*. *Crocus veluchensis* belongs to the same series but is clearly distinguished by the smooth seed surface with vaguely defined polygonal cell walls without relief structures, the

Table 1. Sizes and proportions of seeds – naked seed (without caruncle, funiculus and rapha) and number of papillae per 1000 μm^2 area.

Taxon	length (a), mm	width (b), mm	ratio b/a, %	papilles per 1000 μm^2
Series <i>Flavi</i>				
<i>C. flavus</i>	1.73 – 3.05 2.2 \pm 0.21	1.24 – 2.5 1.77 \pm 0.25	62.3 – 103.8 80.2 \pm 7.3	0 – 3.3 1.2 \pm 0.9
<i>C. olivieri</i>	1.58 – 2 1.76 \pm 0.04	0.96 – 1.61 1.21 \pm 0.13	60.7 – 80.6 68.4 \pm 6.9	1 – 8 1.9 \pm 0.8
Series <i>Scardici</i>				
<i>C. pallasii</i>	1.89 – 3.06 2.51 \pm 0.21	1.59 – 2.6 2.01 \pm 0.18	62.8 – 98 80.9 \pm 11	6.7 – 15.6 9.9 \pm 1.5
Ser. <i>Reticulati</i>				
<i>C. veluchensis</i>	1.97 – 3.14 2.39 \pm 0.3	1.41 – 2.35 1.87 \pm 0.24	58.6 – 106.6 78.9 \pm 11.6	0
<i>C. variegatus</i>	2.31 – 2.52 2.46 \pm 0.09	2.13 – 2.62 2.37 \pm 0.19	84.5 – 104.8 96.3 \pm 8.3	8.9 – 17.8 13.9 \pm 2
<i>C. danubensis</i>	2.46 – 2.52 2.49 \pm 0.04	2.11 – 2.39 2.25 \pm 0.19	85.8 – 95 90.4 \pm 6.5	10 – 17.8 12.8 \pm 2
Ser. <i>Verni</i>				
<i>C. heuffelianus</i>	1.61 – 2.27 2.01 \pm 0.21	1.32 – 2.03 1.63 \pm 0.21	70.6 – 94.9 81.3 \pm 7.1	3.3 – 10 6 \pm 1.78
<i>C. tommasinianus</i>	1.64 – 2.34 2.03 \pm 0.73	1.42 – 2.05 1.75 \pm 0.16	52.8 – 100.3 77.3 \pm 12.1	10 – 17.8 12.8 \pm 2.1
Series <i>Speciosi</i>				
<i>C. pulchellus</i>	1.48 – 2.54 1.9 \pm 0.16	1.2 – 1.88 1.62 \pm 0.13	66.1 – 108.1 86.2 \pm 8.2	7.8 – 18.9 12.3 \pm 3.7
<i>C. speciosus</i>	1.65 – 2.27 1.96 \pm 0.15	1.39 – 2.04 1.75 \pm 0.19	74.9 – 103.2 89.8 \pm 9.5	4.4 – 16.7 9.7 \pm 3.7
Series <i>Biflori</i>				
<i>C. adamioides</i>	1.68 – 2.04 1.85 \pm 0.11	1.15 – 1.63 1.48 \pm 0.15	68.1 – 90.6 79.6 \pm 6.9	13.3 – 26.7 19.3 \pm 3.6
<i>C. randjeloviciorum</i>	0.98 – 1.79 1.44 \pm 0.36	0.96 – 1.54 1.19 \pm 0.25	67.8 – 106.4 84.9 \pm 18.3	6.7 – 12.2 10.4 \pm 1.4
<i>C. chrysanthus</i>	1.66 – 3.28 2.42 \pm 0.24	1.09 – 1.57 1.3 \pm 0.08	44.9 – 65.6 54.7 \pm 5.4	10 – 17.8 12.8 \pm 1.9
<i>C. pallidus</i>	1.69 – 2.1 1.91 \pm 0.19	1.22 – 1.93 1.59 \pm 0.28	71.9 – 96.9 83.2 \pm 10.8	8.9 – 22 \pm 4.4

highly developed caruncle and the fused, slightly developed raphe. Its testa is smooth, without papillae, suggesting the species is phylogenetically distant from *C. variegatus* and *C. danubensis*. This assumption is supported by the floral morphology, which is closer to *C. heuffelianus* in ser. *Verni* (Mathew, 1982). The analysis of the surface coating of the testa makes it possible to distinguish between *C. heuffelianus* and *C. tommasinianus*, which have a

similar structure of the testa, but more or less pronounced differences in the microstructural surface. The testa of *C. tommasinianus* is covered with a dense mass of numerous lingulate hairs with a widened base and a narrowed rounded tip, while in *C. heuffelianus* these hairs are shorter, evenly and sparsely spaced.

The seed surface allows us to distinguish the Bulgarian taxa of ser. *Biflori*. Two of these species

have good differentiation by the density of the papillae – *C. adamioides* (about 19 per 1000 μm^2) and *C. randjeloviciorum* (about 10 per 1000 μm^2). The discrete differences between *C. pallidus* and *C. chrysanthus* exclude the presumption that they are part of the same species. These differences relate not only to the type of seed coat sculpturing but also to the shape and proportions of the seeds and the development of the raphe.

Good characteristics for distinguishing were observed in the members of ser. *Speciosi*, which are closely related, share similar morphology, and are flowering in the autumn. Our results show a clear differentiation by appearance and ornamentation of the seeds. All papillae in the seeds of *C. pulchellus* are narrowly triangular, with a waxy formation at the tip, while in *C. speciosus* they are denser, short and pitted surfaces, without a waxy tip.

Crocus pallasii has the longest hairs compared to the rest of the studied species and corresponds to the taxonomic separation in ser. *Scardici* (Table 1, Fig. 4A). These observations confirm previous studies (Karaismailoğlu et al., 2018).

Crocus flavus and *C. olivieri* do not show both morphological and submicroscopic similarity of the seeds (Fig. 1A, B; Fig. 3A, B). This general difference and the clear macromorphological differences (e.g. corm tunics, stylodia) of the two species, casts doubt on their grouping into ser. *Flavi*.

Overall, the similarity in seed sculpturing supports the confluence of the series *Biflori* and *Verni*.

The results presented so far, demonstrating the heterogeneity and diversity in the morphology of the seeds in the 14 studied species, are suitable for constructing an analytical key for the genus *Crocus* in Bulgaria (Table 2). The taxa are distinguished by shape, size, colouration, development level of the caruncle and raphe, and, above all differences, in sculpturing patterns. Although this parameter is not enough criteria to comment on phylogenetic relationships, the studied species have distinguishable characteristics with suitable diagnostic values.

Analytical key to the Bulgarian members of genus *Crocus* based on the seed morphology

1¹. Seeds large, 1.7–3.2 × 1.2–2.5 mm (measured without the caruncle and raphe). Raphe keel-

- shaped, clearly visible, the entire length of the seed, more than 10 μm wide. Seed surface by \pm large flat cells, without papillae or with spiky or filiform papillae. 2
- 1². Seeds small, 1.6–2.5 × 1–2 mm (without the caruncle and raphe), sometimes up to 3.3 mm long, but then cylindrically elongated. Raphe not keel-shaped, narrower than 10 μm . Seminal surface by \pm small cells drawn into short, conical or tongue-like papillae. 4
- 2¹. Seeds ovate, \pm laterally flattened. Testa surface composed by relatively regular flat hexagonal cells, smooth, without papillae or mammillae, resulting in a \pm shiny surface. Caruncle relatively large. Raphe distinct, keel-shaped. *C. veluchensis*
- 2². Seeds rotundate or ovate. Seed testa with long filiform or spiky papillae, with a shiny hairy or velvety surface. 3
- 3¹. Seeds \pm spherical, with a well-developed raphe extended towards the caruncle and funiculus. Seed surface with singly arranged cylindric-acuminate hairs (0–3 per 1000 μm^2), which give it a glossy-fibrous appearance. *C. flavus*
- 3². Seeds \pm ovoid, with a keel-shaped raphe not expanded into the caruncle and funiculus. Seed surface with densely arranged filiform hairs (7–16 per 1000 μm^2), which give it a velvety appearance. *C. pallasii*
- 4¹. Seeds elongate, 1.7–3.3 × 1–1.6 mm, more than 2 times longer than wide, without a developed caruncle. Seed surface covered by long conical papillae with expanded base and secondary cuticular overlays at the apex. *C. chrysanthus*
- 4². Seeds ovate or rotundate, 1–2.6 × 1–2.4 mm, up to 1.5 times longer than wide, with a \pm developed caruncle. 6
- 5¹. Caruncle \pm dorso-ventrally flattened, not separated from the seed. Raphe, funiculus and caruncle slightly darker than the rest of the seed. Seed surface by small cells, each mammillose in appearance (with densely spaced dome-shaped outgrowths with secondary single punctate structures), 1–7 per 1000 μm^2 resulting in \pm rough-shiny surface. *C. olivieri*
- 5². Caruncle of a different shape. Seed surface by small cells with short papillae,

	3–27 per 1000 μm^2 , resulting in the seed with a dull surface	5
6 ¹ .	Seeds with flattened ventral and swollen dorsal side.	7
6 ² .	Seeds \pm oval or spherical in shape.	10
7 ¹ .	Papillae lingulate flattened, with expanded base.	8
7 ² .	Papillae conical, not flattened, with with or without expanded base.	9
8 ¹ .	Papillae flat, with expanded base and twist at tip, 3–10 per 1000 μm^2 of seed surface. <i>C. heuffelianus</i>	
8 ² .	Papillae squamate-lingulate, with parallel folds, 10–18 per 1000 μm^2 of seed surface. <i>C. tommasinianus</i>	
9 ¹ .	Testa cells with conical papillae pointed into thinner cuticular tips. <i>C. pulchellus</i>	
9 ² .	Testa cells densely spaced, conical, irregularly folded lengthwise, forming papillae with rounded apex. <i>C. speciosus</i>	
10 ¹ .	Seeds rotundate, longer than 2.2 mm and wider than 2 mm. Raphe convex, visible as a suture.	11
10 ² .	Seeds ovate, shorter than 2.2 mm and narrower than 2 mm. Raphe barely noticeable.	12
11 ¹ .	Papillae \pm conical, elongated into pointed cuticular tips, with secondary cuticular apical overlays. <i>C. danubensis</i>	
11 ² .	Papillae \pm wavy, lingulate, without pointed tips, and without cuticular overlays. <i>C. variegatus</i>	
12 ¹ .	Papillae short oval swellings, without tips. <i>C. pallidus</i>	
12 ² .	Papillae pyramidate or conical, with pointed cuticular tips.	13
13 ¹ .	Papillae narrowly conical, closely spaced, 13–27 per 1000 μm^2 <i>C. adamioides</i>	
13 ² .	Papillae broadly pyramidate, wavy arranged, 7–12 per 1000 μm^2 <i>C. randjeloviciorum</i>	

Conclusion

Although there is great diversity in the sculptural structures of testa seeds, there is no unique morphology for taxa in each series due to overlapping characters within these taxa. Seed micromorphology alone cannot provide information for constructing phylogenetic relationships in *Crocus*, but it provides compa-

rable parameters for determination in disputed taxa with closely related and obscure floral and vegetative morphology. The macro and micromorphology of seeds provide clear distinguishable structures to distinguish *C. variegata* from *C. danubensis*, and *C. veluchensis* from *C. heuffelianus*. The study provides data on the seed morphology of the recently discovered *C. heuffelianus*, *C. speciosus* and *C. adamioides* in Bulgaria.

In future research, it would be useful to increase the sample size and include taxa from critical groups that occur outside the territory of Bulgaria and to evaluate the consistency in seed structures and discreteness in the taxonomy of genus *Crocus*.

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